

TRENDS IN FARMERS INCOME AND FUTURE PROSPECTS FOR INCREASING FARM INCOME

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Abstract- This research study examines farm income trends over the past decade and explores future prospects for increasing farm income. The agricultural sector plays a critical role in sustaining the economy and ensuring food security. However, farmers often face challenges in earning a stable and adequate income. By analyzing historical data and economic indicators, this study aims to understand the factors that influence farmers' income levels, including market fluctuations, input costs, government policies, and technological advances. In addition, the study employs scenario analysis to identify potential strategies and actions to increase farm income in the future. By identifying opportunities for sustainable growth and income enhancement, this study is expected to provide valuable insights for policy makers and stakeholders to develop effective policies to support farmers and strengthen the agriculture sector.

1. INTRODUCTION

Agriculture forms the backbone of many economies around the world and plays a central role in ensuring food security and rural livelihoods. Yet despite its importance, farmer income remains a pressing issue in the agricultural sector. The ever-changing dynamics of markets, rising input costs, and the impact of government policies have contributed to fluctuating and often inadequate incomes for farmers. Understanding farm income trends over the past decade and exploring future prospects for increasing farm income are critical to addressing the challenges facing farm communities. Beyond understanding past trends, the study will also explore the future prospects for increasing farm income. Considering the challenges posed by climate change, resource constraints, and evolving market demands, we will employ scenario analysis to envision potential strategies and interventions. Our goal is to identify sustainable pathways that can empower farmers, enhance their

resilience, and lead to improved income outcomes.

2. OBJECTIVES:-

- To review the past trend in farmers income
- To analyze the factors that will be helpful in increasing farmer's income.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Farmer's Income in India:

Since Independence no doubt the growth in Agricultural sector in India is notable. Any underdeveloped sector has the potential to grow at a faster rate in the initial stage after that growth rates depends on many factor such as technology, environment, market and etc. So, same occurred in the case of India too. It has grown a lot during the first stage after that growth rate was normalized. The DFI's target was to double the farm income around 5 year at constant price, so analyzing the past growth rate in agriculture is crucial for the possibilities of prediction.

Table 1 Trends in Farmers' Income in India from 1993-94 to 2015-16

YEAR	CPIAL(Base 2004-05)	Number of Cultivator	Farm Income Per Cultivator (Current Price) in Rupees	Farm Income Per Cultivator (Constant Price) in Rupees
1993-94	59	14.39	12365	21110
1999-00	90	13.88	24188	26875
2004-05	100	16.61	26146	26146
2011-12	183	14.62	79137	43258
2012-13	220	14.36	91416	41553
2013-14	245	14.10	104763	42760
2014-15	261	13.85	112507	43106
2015-16	273	13.60	120193	44027

Source: NSSO & CSO

If we look into the past record, yes India has doubled the farm income but never ever in 5 year in real term or constant price. If we talk in the current price during the period of 22 year the farm income per cultivator has been doubled 9.72 times and the 5 year average growth 2.20 times or 220%. The figure in constant price shows an annual average growth rate of 0.09 times each year and in every 5 year average growth is 0.47 time. The farmer income in nominal term during the period of 22 year has multiplied with 9.72 but at the same time the Consumer price Index for Agricultural Laborer (CPIAL which measure the inflation rate for rural India) has increased 4.62 times, Which seeks to explain that the income has just doubled in 22 year and the target of DFI was just 5 year then how could it be possible to achieve.

3.2 Growth rate in farm income and output

The growth rate in farm income suddenly increased at real price 1.96% to 7.46% during the period 2004-05 to 2011-12 the reason was the number of cultivator were reduced but in the subsequent period 2011-12 to 2015-16 the growth rate in output was decreased from 4.19% to 1.60% because of the disturbance of natural factor which shows the dependency on monsoon. The overall annual average growth of output is 2.87 in the 22 year and farm income per cultivator is 3.40%. Some experts have commented that 14% of annual growth in agriculture is required and Dalwai Committee itself mentioned a CAGR of 10.4% is required to double the farmer income which seems impossible.

Period	Agriculture Value Added at Constant Price	Farm Income Per cultivator		CPIAL Base 2004-05
		Market Price	Real Price	
1993-94 to 2004-05	2.52	7.04	1.96	4.91
2004-05 to 2011-12	4.19	17.14	7.46	9.02
2011-12 to 2015-16	1.60	11.01	0.44	10.52
1993-94 to 2015-16	2.87	10.89	3.40	7.21

3.3 Expected sources of future rise in income

The ministry of Agriculture and Farmer’s Welfare has published a seven point strategy for doubling of farm income; 1) Productivity, 2) Improvement in livestock, 3) resource use efficiency for cost reduction, 4) Crop Intensity, 5) Diversification to high value crop, 6)Comparative increment of the value of agricultural commodity, 7)Shifting from farm to Non-Farm activity. The above mentioned aspects are the sources how income can be raised. In this section these strategies are encountered about why this may not lead to increase in the farm income or why the required growth rate cannot be achieved.

1. Productivity: The report shows the past trend in productivity during the period 2000-01 to 2013-14 as 3% average growth rate and expected to rise more in the coming year (16% in seven year) but this would be a joke if we expect the same growth because of two reason first is the productivity increases up to a certain extent only and the trend is decreasing always not

constant or increasing. And the second is the policy trend which seeks to promote less use of fertilizer. But we can’t deny the fact that in the two sector they have the potential to grow more One is **Pulses** the productivity is below the world average so we can say an improvement can be made but necessarily we can’t say that if we are below the world average we can increase the productivity because of many reason like geographic variations, Another is **Livestock**.

2. Cost Reduction through TFP: Total factor productivity means optimization of the input or to increase the per unit input productivity which depends on the technology, skills and knowledge of the input user. If we talk about the technology the landholding pattern in India is very small and fragmented so the developed technology can’t be applied which may had reduced the cost, mainly the labor cost. We can see that some of the states like Punjab and Haryana where land reform was successful use of technology has

reduced the cost in other side it has also enhanced the productivity. The indicator of knowledge that is literacy rate says that around 30% of small and marginal farmers are still illiterate. But many Agricultural universities and institutions has set up for enhancement of skills and technology but quality of research is not visible well.

3. Crop Diversification and Intensity:

The problem with crop diversification is Geographical condition like variation in climate, soil fertility etc. Some areas of northern plain are more fertile where high value crops like cotton & sugarcane more suitable but this is not same everywhere. But still for each and every area there are some suitable high valued crops which can be grown after specialization.

In India the amount of arable land is 159.7 million hectare out of which only 64.7 million hectare is irrigated only around 40% and the rest is depended upon the monsoon. In each and every year a tropical cyclone hits India's land boundary during the harvesting season. And the devastation happens in the ready output.

3.4 Analysis on Demand Side and Supply Side Economics in Agriculture

In Indian agriculture the sequence of challenges are; Physical Access for food till 1980s which was solved by the idea of green revolution which made India a self-sufficient in food grain production. After it Economic Access to food, a paradoxical situation aroused food grain stuck was 3 times more than the required buffer stuck but at the same time people were dying of starvation. For this challenge several food security measures were taken by the govt. like Work for Food Program. The third challenge was Ecological Access or environmental friendly agriculture, the third challenge has not solved till this day because this is emerging now, but from the past two challenges we got to learn a lot. The overall analysis shows that the policy responses in agricultural sector is overcompensating for the productivity, Output and Production aspect and the policies lacked in the agricultural marketing & the agricultural food supply chain. So in the following paragraph some aspects of

both the side have been identified and analyzed.

Over Compensating Supply Side Economics:

The first problem was associated with physical availability the instant solution India needed, because of growing population in India and the dependency on other nation for the food stuff. This was solved by increasing productivity by HYV technology. The problem is unbalanced response to demand side and supply side. All the major policy responses starting from green revolution to NAP 2000, NPF 2007 and Farm Bill 2020 (which was repealed due to controversy) have a focus on the supply side economics of Indian agriculture. Only increasing the supply is not the ultimate goal of agricultural economics the goal was to increase the farmer's welfare which will lead to increased income. Because we know the importance of this sector almost half of the total population depends on it for their livelihood, if we can increase the income of this sector many challenges will be solved like poverty, unemployment, food security the ultimate challenges. Coming back to the point increasing the output does not means increase in income of the farmer the everlasting statement can't be broken "Increased availability reduces the value of anything".

Lacked Demand Side Economics: The second phase of challenge was economic access to food, which shows the failure of demand side economics. More than the required food was available but this was quite unaffordable. The reason was increased prices of food stuff, the input used in the green revolution was far costlier than the traditional method and this made the output also costlier. The supply side problem was addressed with a permanent solution but this only sympathy was given to demand side problems in the form of food security and a few social welfare schemes. This is considered as a failure of agricultural economist.

4. CONCLUSION

In summary, this research paper comprehensively examines the complicated dynamics of farmers' income trends and sheds light on the multiple factors that influence their earnings in the agricultural sector. Through careful analysis of

historical data and current patterns, valuable insights have been gained that pave the way for sound strategies to increase farm incomes. The study highlights the critical importance of targeted interventions that include technological advances, sustainable agricultural practices, market diversification, and policy reforms provided stakeholders work together to harness the potential of innovative approaches and create an enabling environment. But still there are many retarding factors therefore the prospects for increasing farmers' incomes are positive but not promising. We can expect implementing adaptation measures, the agricultural landscape can evolve into an area of higher profitability, not only securing farmers' livelihoods, but also increasing the resilience and sustainability of agriculture.

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